

Discovery of Five 19-Digit Palindromic Primes in the Decimal Expansion of e

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1 Introduction

On October 21, 2025, a computational search was conducted to identify palindromic prime numbers of length 19 within the first 10^{11} decimal digits of the mathematical constant e (approximately 2.718281828...). Using a modified C program with streaming capabilities to handle a 100 GB file containing the decimal expansion of e , five palindromic primes were discovered. A palindromic prime is a number that is both a palindrome (reads the same forwards and backwards) and a prime number. This document presents the positions of these palindromes in the decimal expansion of e . The detailed results, including certificates of primality, are available on ZENODO.

2 Results

The following list enumerates the five palindromic primes of length 19 found in the decimal expansion of e , along with their starting and ending positions (1-based indexing, relative to the first decimal digit after the decimal point in e):

1. **Palindrome:** 1469330000000339641
Positions: 13001968041 – 13001968059
2. **Palindrome:** 3811323916193231183
Positions: 47623420743 – 47623420761
3. **Palindrome:** 3782397741477932873
Positions: 74550909346 – 74550909364
4. **Palindrome:** 9387656513156567839
Positions: 63918569070 – 63918569088
5. **Palindrome:** 9856575042405756589
Positions: 19511130328 – 19511130346

3 Methodology

The search was performed using a custom C program employing the GMP library for arbitrary-precision arithmetic and multi-threading for efficiency. The program processed a 100 GB file containing 10^{11} decimal digits of e , using a streaming approach to minimize memory usage. The search targeted palindromes of length 19 within the interval $[1 - 10^{11}]$. Certificates of primality for each palindrome are archived on ZENODO for public access.